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INFLUENCE OF *JAPONISME*, AND MUSICAL ELEMENTS
IN THE SERIES OF PAINTINGS *SONATA OF THE SPRING*
BY M. K. ČIURLIONIS

The influence of *Japonisme* on the paintings of Mikalojus Konstantinas Čiurlionis (1875–1911), his contemporaries, and European Impressionist painters has been briefly researched since 2011 and has been mentioned frequently in articles by the present author. This article first reconsiders the influence of *Japonisme* on a series of paintings by Čiurlionis, *Sonata of the Spring*, which apparently derive from the Japanese *ukiyo-e*, woodblock prints and *Nikuhitsu-ga*, Japanese original paintings in the Feliks Jasiński collection, which Čiurlionis most likely saw during his stay in Poland. Next, since these paintings “Allegro”, “Andante”, “Scherzo”, and “Finale” have musical titles, the article considers why he decided to give musical titles to his paintings, and the relationship between those titles and the composition of the paintings as well as the musical elements found in them.

Keywords: Čiurlionis, Whistler, Landsbergis, Hokusai, Hiroshige, *ukiyo-e*, *Japonisme*.

1. Introduction

The *Japonisme* tendency in Čiurlionis’ paintings was first mentioned in an article “Mikalojus Konstantinas Čiurlionis, the Lithuanian Composer and Painter, and the Correlation between Pictorial and Musical Compositions” by Ichiro Kato (1930–2003), published in 1976. In the article, Kato pointed out that Čiurlionis’s “Finale” from *Sonata of the Sea* (1908, Fig. 1-1) has similarities to Katsushika Hokusai’s (1760–1849) *ukiyo-e*, a woodblock print, *The Great Wave off Kanagawa* from *Thirty-Six Views of Mount Fuji* (ca. 1831–33, Fig. 1-2) and he presumed that it would be a direct influence from the famous Japanese *ukiyo-e*. This theory has been received favourably and accepted generally as an established theory to the present. However, Kato did not consider how Čiurlionis came to know Hokusai’s work. Therefore, since 2011, I have researched how

Fig. 1-1 M. K. Čiurlionis. *Sonata of the Sea. Finale*. 1908. Paper, tempera.

Fig. 1-2 Katsushika Hokusai. *Thirty-Six Views of Mount Fuji. The Great Wave off Kanagawa*. ca. 1831-33. Woodblock print.

Čiurlionis came to encounter Japanese *ukiyo-e* and have investigated whether other works by Čiurlionis were influenced by *Japonisme*.

From my research studies, it appears evident that there were two probable occasions when Čiurlionis saw the *ukiyo-e*: the first exhibition was of Japanese *ukiyo-e* prints held in J. Kriwult's salon in 1900-01 and the second was at the beginning of 1901, at the exhibition of Feliks Jasiński's famous collection of Japanese arts, both of which were held in Warsaw during his stay there.¹ In addition to the above, it is obvious that his travels to museums in Prague, Dresden, Nuremberg, Munich, and Vienna in 1906 supported by Bronisława Wolman had a great influence on his later creative activities.

It is a well-known fact that the period between 1906 and 1908 was the most productive period for Čiurlionis as a composer, painter, and writer. From the beginning of 1906, he lived in Druskininkai and began arranging Lithuanian folk songs. In a letter to his brother Povilas, he declared, "(I will) dedicate all my past and future works to Lithuania". In addition, the idea of composing a Lithuanian opera was even born.

1 Alber, Z., 1990, pp.14-17.

In May 1906 Čiurlionis joined an exhibition of works by students of the Warsaw School of Art in St Petersburg, exhibiting his cycles *Creation of the World*, *A Day and Storm*, the diptych *Rex* (now lost), and others, which were well received by critics, who said “they were the most outstanding works ever produced”.²

In 1907, he undertook several music projects, completing the orchestration of his symphonic poem *The Sea*, and starting work on the new symphonic poem *Creation of the World*. In the autumn of that year, he moved to Vilnius and joined the assembly as an executive board member of the Society of the Lithuanian Art. At that time, Čiurlionis had met his future wife Sofija Kymantaitė at the dress rehearsal for Gabrielius Landsbergis-Žemkalnis’ drama *Blinda*.³

Surprisingly, in 1907 (mostly in the first half of that year), Čiurlionis created more than 50 paintings: *Sonata of the Sun*, the triptychs *Raigardas*, *My Road*, *The Prince’s Journey*, *Summer*, the cycle of eight paintings *Winter*, *The Zodiac cycle*, and the painting *Forest*, etc. His four paintings “Allegro”, “Andante”, “Scherzo”, and “Finale” from the series *Sonata of the Spring* were painted in the same year in 1907, along with these paintings.⁴

2. Influence of Japonisme on Čiurlionis’s “Finale” from *Sonata of the Spring*

Rather than start ‘at the beginning’ with the first movement of the Sonata, we will first consider the influence of Utagawa Hiroshige’s (1797–1858)’s *ukiyo-e* woodblock print in Čiurlionis’s “Finale” from the *Sonata of the Spring*. In fact, “Finale” was not the first of Čiurlionis’s paintings to be influenced by Hiroshige’s *ukiyo-e* print. Therefore, before introducing the “Finale”, let us recall three Čiurlionis’s paintings which are thought to be influenced by Hiroshige’s *ukiyo-e* prints (as per my research published in 2015), all of which were included in the Feliks Jasiński collection.

2 Zubovas, R. 2010, *Biography*. Available at: < <http://ciurlionis.eu/en/ciurlionis/> >.

3 *Ibid.*

4 Zubovas, R. 2010, *Biography*. Available at: < <http://ciurlionis.eu/en/ciurlionis/> >.

Fig. 2-1 M. K. Čiurlionis. *Raigardas* (triptych). 1907. Paper, tempera.

Fig. 2-2 Utagawa Hiroshige. *Famous Views of the Eastern Capital. Whole View of Asukayama* (triptych). c. 1835–39. Woodblock print.

Among Čiurlionis's paintings from 1907, the most striking is a triptych *Raigardas* (1907, Fig. 2-1), which shows the strong influence of Hiroshige's triptych *Whole View of Asukayama* from *Famous Views of the Eastern Capital* (c. 1835–39, Fig. 2-2). The influence of Hiroshige is evident in the form of this “triptych” and the bird's-eye view technique.⁵

In addition, like Van Gogh, Whistler, and the Polish painters, Čiurlionis was especially influenced by *ukiyo-e* prints of Hiroshige which are from the

5 Nunokawa, Y. 2015, p. 95.

Fig. 3-1 Utagawa Hiroshige. *One Hundred Famous Views of Edo. Sudden Shower over Shin-Ōhashi Bridge and Atake*. 1857. Woodblock print.

Fig. 3-2 M. K. Čiurlionis. *Summer*. 1907. Canvas, tempera.

series *One Hundred Famous Views of Edo* (1856–58). So let's now look at some examples from this series of Hiroshige's *ukiyo-e* that might have influenced Čiurlionis.

The first one is Hiroshige's *Sudden Shower over Shin-Ōhashi Bridge and Atake* (1857, Fig. 3-1) which might have influenced Čiurlionis's painting *Summer* (1907, Fig. 3-2). The black rain clouds at the top of the painting and the depiction of rain falling in lines across the painting could be said to be influenced by Hiroshige.⁶ The second is Hiroshige's *Susaki and the Jūmantsubo Plain near Fukagawa* (1856–58, Fig. 4-1) which might have also influenced Čiurlionis's painting "Fairy Tale No. 2" from his triptych *Fairy Tale* (1907, Fig. 4-2). The

6 *Ibid.*, p. 89.

Fig. 4-1 Utagawa Hiroshige. *One Hundred Famous Views of Edo. Susaki and the Jūmansubō Plain near Fukagawa.* 1856–1858. Woodblock print.

Fig. 4-2 M. K. Čiurlionis. *Fairy Tale (trptych). No. 2.* 1907. Paper, tempera.

depiction of a bird flying in the sky with its wings spread wide might also be said to be influenced by Hiroshige.⁷

Like the above three works – a triptych *Raigardas, Summer*, “Fairy Tale No. 2” from triptych *Fairy Tale* by Čiurlionis – “Finale” painted in the same year was probably influenced by Hiroshige. As we compare Hiroshige’s *The City Flourishing, the Tanabata Festival* from *One Hundred Famous Views of Edo* (1856–58, Fig. 5-1) and Čiurlionis’s “Finale” from *Sonata of the Spring* (1907, Fig. 5-2), the similarities could be found between the colourful papers or small flags flying in spiral in both images.⁸

7 *Ibid.*, p. 95.

8 Nunokawa, Y. 2015, p. 95.

Fig. 5-1 Utagawa Hiroshige. *One Hundred Famous Views of Edo. The City Flourishing, the Tanabata Festival*. 1856–1858. Woodblock print.

Fig. 5-2 M. K. Čiurlionis. *Sonata of the Spring. Finale*. 1907. Paper, tempera.

3. Influence of Japonisme on Scherzo from “Sonata of the Spring”

The theme of this conference, “Sonata of the Spring”, gave me the opportunity to examine again the Feliks Jasiński collection, which Čiurlionis most likely saw in person. Through that re-examination, I discovered some new perspectives between Čiurlionis’ painting “Scherzo” from *Sonata of the Spring* (1907, Fig. 6-1) and Watanabe Seitei’s (1852–1918) *Nikuhitsu-ga*, a Japanese original painting titled *Summer. Blooming wisteria and fish* (ca. 1891, Fig. 6-2) as well as Hiroshige’s *ukiyo-e The Exquisite Sea Foods of the Eastern Capital* (Fig. 6-3). The way Seitei depicts fish using ink shading is somewhat similar to Čiurlionis’ light-colored monochrome depiction of fish. In addition, the fishing nets de-

Fig. 6-1 M. K. Čiurlionis. *Sonata of the Spring. Scherzo*. 1907. Paper, tempera.

Fig. 6-2 Watanabe Seitei. *Summer: Blooming wisteria and fish*. ca. 1891. Colour painting on silk. The National Museum, Kraków

picted in Hiroshige's *ukiyo-e* might also have influenced Čiurlionis' "Scherzo". Further evidence that Čiurlionis may have seen this work by Seitei is the latter artist's depiction of the wisteria flowers, which appears to have influenced Čiurlionis's *Winter VIII* from the cycle of eight paintings *Winter* (1907, Fig. 6-4), painted in the same year as "Scherzo". Although it is impossible to say for certain that Čiurlionis's "Scherzo" was influenced by the works of Seitei and Hiroshige, the fact that these works were included in the Jasiński collection strongly suggests this possibility.

4. Regarding Whistler's *Japonisme* paintings with musical titles

As mentioned in my article written in 2015, the paintings by the American-born painter James Abbott McNeill Whistler (1834–1903) are probably

Fig. 6-3 Utagawa Hiroshige. *The Exquisite Sea Foods of the Eastern Capital*. Woodblock print. The National Museum, Kraków

Fig. 6-4 M. K. Čiurlionis. *Winter* (cycle of 8 paintings). No. 8. 1907. Paper, tempera.

the most famous examples of *Japonisme* paintings with musical titles such as *Variations*, *Symphony* and *Nocturne*. Whistler was also an ardent collector of Japanese art, and he himself left many paintings that show the influence of *Japonisme* from Japanese art and *ukiyo-e* by Hiroshige. Čiurlionis's colleagues in Poland, who studied at art schools throughout Europe, were also influenced by Whistler's paintings and created many *Japonisme* paintings. Therefore, it is very likely that Čiurlionis knew about Whistler's paintings through his Polish colleagues and might have been influenced by Whistler's *Japonisme* paintings with musical titles.

Although Čiurlionis' colleagues in Poland such as Olga Boznańska (1865–1940) and Wojciech Weiss (1875–1950) showed the influence of *Japonisme* in their paintings, what they were interested in were mainly Japanese costumes and artifacts such as *kimono* and typical Japanese *uchiwa* [fan]. However, what Čiurlionis adopted from Hiroshige's *ukiyo-e* prints were the night scenes which were different from his colleagues'.

Along with *Japonisme* paintings with musical titles, the artist who created paintings of night scenes was again Whistler. We can easily recognize the influ-

Fig. 7-1 Utagawa Hiroshige. *One Hundred Famous Views of Edo. Kyōbashi Takegashi*. 1857. Woodblock print.

Fig. 7-2 J. A. M. Whistler. *Nocturne: Blue and Gold – Old Battersea Bridge*. ca. 1872–75. Canvas, oil. Tate Britain, London

ence from Hiroshige's *Kyōbashi takegashi* from *One Hundred Famous Views of Edo* (1857, Fig. 7-1) in Whistler's *Nocturne: Blue and Gold - Old Battersea Bridge* (ca. 1872–75, Fig. 7-2). What inspired Whistler here was the unique composition adopting a bridge pier in the middle of the painting and the peculiar viewpoint from the river beneath its arches. These innovative tactics were unseen in earlier Western paintings. The characteristic faded blue tone evoking the silence of the night was undoubtedly taken from Hiroshige's example.⁹

What is noteworthy here is this faded blue tone was also seen in Čiurlionis's *Sea at Night* painted in 1906 (Fig. 7-3). This seems to find parallels with

9 Nunokawa, Y. 2015, p. 90.

Fig. 7-3 M. K. Čiurlionis. *Sea at Night*. 1906. Paper, Tempera on cardboard.

Fig. 7-4 J. A. M. Whistler. *Nocturne: Blue and Silver – Chelsea*. 1871.
Oil paint on wood. Tate Britain, London

Fig. 7-5 J. M. W. Turner. *Nocturne: Blue and Silver - Cremorne Lights*. 1872. Canvas, oil. Tate Britain, London

Whistler's *Japonisme* paintings of night scenes such as *Nocturne: Blue and Silver - Chelsea* (1871, Fig. 7-4) and *Nocturne: Blue and Silver - Cremorne Lights* (1872, Fig. 7-5). It is not certain if Čiurlionis knew these Whistler night scene paintings with musical titles; however, it is clear that he had the same artistic intention as Whistler.

In Whistler's well-known *Nocturne in Black and Gold: The Falling Rocket* (1874) (Fig. 8-1), pictorial ambiguity caused a great deal of controversy. Some resemblances with Hiroshige's *Fireworks at Ryōgoku* from *One Hundred Famous Views of Edo* (1856–58, Fig. 8-2) are also seen in the common subject matter and its rendering (these resemblances have been pointed out by many scholars: Child (1889), Pennell (1911) and Ono (2003)).¹⁰ Here Whistler learned how to express the “night music” through the interweaving of black colour, light and shade. Thus, the innovative motifs from Hiroshige's *ukiyo-e* made it possible

¹⁰ Nunokawa, Y. 2015, pp. 90-91.

Fig. 8-1 J. A. M. Whistler. *Nocturne in Black and Gold: The Falling Rocket*. ca. 1875. Canvas, oil. Detroit Institute of Arts

Fig. 8-2 Utagawa Hiroshige. *One Hundred Famous Views of Edo. Fireworks at Ryōgoku*. 1856–58. Woodblock print.

for Whistler to express his nocturnal idea that “a nocturne is an arrangement of line, form, and colour first” in his paintings. Here we could see how much Whistler got closer to musical thinking in art, which is a gateway to abstract paintings of the coming generation in the early 20th century.

Čiurlionis’ *Sketch for a Composition* (1908, Fig. 8-3) shows strong influence from the above-mentioned Hiroshige’s *Fireworks at Ryōgoku* (1856-58). In the Čiurlionis sketch, a person on a ship is looking at the sky with stars. The depiction of the stars seems remarkably similar to Hiroshige’s. Moreover, Čiurlionis transferred the stars into his “Allegro” from *Sonata of the Sea* (1908, Fig. 8-4). Again, what is noteworthy here is that, in a manner similar to

Fig. 8-3 M. K. Čiurlionis. *Sketch for a Composition*. 1908. Pencil on Paper.

Fig. 8-4 M. K. Čiurlionis. *Sonata No. 5 (Sonata of the Sea). Allegro*. 1908. Paper, tempera.

Whistler's example, Čiurlionis provided a musical title "Allegro" from *Sonata of the Sea* for the painting. From this point of view, Čiurlionis might have known Whistler's painting.¹¹

5. Influence of *Japonisme* and musical elements in "Allegro" from *Sonata of the Spring*

This Čiurlionis "Allegro" is an extremely unique work. The suggestive depiction of monochrome by only blurring the shades of pigment without using contour lines is almost unprecedented in the history of Western painting. This technique is very similar to the new trend of ink painting that began in the 13th century during the Southern Song dynasty (1127–1279) in China (A Chinese Chan Buddhist monk and painter, Muqi (ca. 1210–69) is said to have been the founder of this trend) and Japanese ink painting from the *Muromachi* period (1336–1573) that was influenced by this trend. Although Muqi's ink paintings had not yet been imported to Europe at that time, Čiurlionis may have seen Japanese 18th

11 *Ibid.*

Fig. 9-1 Katsushika Hokusai. *Thirty-Six Views of Mount Fuji. Mount Fuji Viewed during a Fine Wind on a Clear Morning*. ca. 1830–32. Woodblock print.

Fig. 9-2 M. K. Čiurlionis. *Spring Motif*. 1907. Paper, tempera.

or 19th century paintings after Muqi’s style in the Jasieński collection, which was probably imported to Europe at that time. It is undeniable that Čiurlionis might have learned about these Japanese ink paintings through some means.

However, as I have mentioned in my previous research since 2011, the influence from Katsushika Hokusai (1760–1849) also cannot be denied. In addition to *The Great Wave off Kanagawa* from *Thirty-Six Views of Mount Fuji* (Fig. 1-2) we saw at the beginning of this article, the dots of clouds in the blue sky in Hokusai’s *Mount Fuji Viewed during a Fine Wind on a Clear Morning* from *Thirty-Six Views of Mount Fuji* (ca. 1830–32, Fig. 9-1) are very similar to the dots of clouds in Čiurlionis’s painting *Spring Motif* (1907, Fig. 9-2) which was painted in the same year as “Allegro” from *Sonata of the Spring*.¹²

Furthermore, please take a look at Čiurlionis’s “Allegro” from *Sonata of the Spring* (1907, Fig. 10-1), and Hokusai’s *ukiyo-e Ejiri in Suruga Province* from *Thirty-Six Views of Mount Fuji* (ca. 1830–32, Fig. 10-2). Although the details are different, the shape and direction of the trees bending before the wind as well as the composition of the path in the field of reeds seen in Hokusai’s *ukiyo-e* are

12 Nunokawa, Y. 2015, p. 95.

Fig. 10-1 M. K. Čiurlionis. *Sonata of the Spring. Allegro*. 1907. Paper, tempera.

Fig. 10-2 Katsushika Hokusai. *Thirty-Six Views of Mount Fuji. Ejiri in Suruga Province*. ca. 1830-1832. Woodblock print.

seemed to be reflected in Čiurlionis’s “Allegro”. Or, if we focus only on the trees fluttering in the wind, it looks as if Hiroshige’s *ukiyo-e* *The City Flourishing, the Tanabata Festival* from *One Hundred Famous Views of Edo* (1856-58, Fig. 5-1), of which a fragment was also used in Čiurlionis’s *Finale*, also adopts only the bamboo parts in this *Allegro*.

However, this raises a question. Although Čiurlionis painted this painting in monochrome, Hokusai’s *ukiyo-e* is colored in blue. So, why did Čiurlionis paint this painting in monochrome? One of my hypotheses is that this is because Čiurlionis was trying to paint a musical score in his painting. One of the reasons I came up with this hypothesis was because I had read a theory by Landsbergis in his book “Čiurlionis: Time and Content” published in 1992 in which Čiurlionis’s musical melodic patterns are represented with linear equivalents in the composition and detail of his painting. Let me quote his ideas:

In 1962-1965, this author [Prof. Vytautas Landsbergis], as a performing artist, became increasingly aware of the way in which Čiurlionis’s piano compositions from different periods exhibited certain recurring characteristic melodic patterns with linear equivalents in the composition and detail of his painting. Schematical-

Fig. 10-3 From Vytautas Landsbergis. "M. K. Čiurlionis: Time and Content" (page 116, 1992), Lituanus, Vilnius

Fig. 10-4 From Vytautas Landsbergis. "M. K. Čiurlionis: Time and Content" (page 117, 1992), Lituanus, Vilnius

ly, without copying from any particular work, this pattern can be represented as follows (Fig. 10-3):

In his painting, such a pattern can be seen in the arrangement of the silhouettes of mountains, clouds, and forest. The pattern is often modified into a vertical, more steeply rising variant with hints of anthropomorphism, offering at once a profounder psychological foundation and a sense of unconscious symbol. This phenomenon is echoed by the presence of analogous patterns in his music (primarily in melodies of the higher registers, in the upper layer of the text).

On the other hand, the basso ostinato in his piano works is characterized not only by a rhythm based on the duration of a sound but also by its linear features, schematically described in the following ways (Fig. 10-4):

For those examples, melodies of a smooth movement of the eights have been chosen (from Prelude VL-266 and the piece *The Nightingale*, VL-268), arranging on the vertical and horizontal axes the sound-points according to the arbitrarily unified smallest element of division: a half-tone or an eight. [...] Čiurlionis's imagination gave birth to several basic graphic patterns that then found their way by various channels into the artist's line and the composer's melody. Their equivalents are not just analogies in separate works; each time they are expressions of a more assured and definitive graphic prototype.¹³

13 Landsbergis, V. 1992, pp. 115–118.

Left: Fig. 10-5 M. K. Čiurlionis. *Sonata of the Spring, Allegro*. 1907. Paper, tempera.

Right: Fig. 10-5 M. K. Čiurlionis. "Prelude in f-moll", DK 251/ VL 307 (1907). From D. Kučinskas. "Čiurlionis: Piano Works (Urtext)" (2011), Yamaha Music Corporation, Tokyo

After reading this theory by Prof. Landsbergis, I came to the hypothesis that Čiurlionis was trying to represent musical notation, or music, in this monochrome painting *Allegro*.

In fact, Čiurlionis had a series of 13 paintings entitled "The Creation of the World" painted in Warsaw 1905–6, and soon after that, in Druskininkai 1907 he began to compose a musical work with the same title, a Symphonic Poem "Creation of the World". Although these works do not have musical titles, it is clear that from that time on he was trying to express music through painting.

In the summer of 1907, he painted several series of sonatas in Druskininkai, and at the same time he was composing several complex piano pieces such as Preludes VL 306, 307, 308 and 309. Therefore, we can assume that Čiurlionis was composing music and painting at almost the same time.

So here, please compare Čiurlionis' painting "Allegro" with the music score of his "Prelude in f-moll" VL 307 (Fig. 10-5), which he composed in

Left: Fig. 11-1 M. K. Čiurlionis. *Sonata of the Spring. Andante*. 1907. Paper, tempera.

Right: Fig. 11-2 M. K. Čiurlionis. "Prelude in d-moll", DK 252/ VL 308 (1907). From D. Kučinskas. "Čiurlionis: Piano Works (Urtext)" (2011), Yamaha Music Corporation, Tokyo

Druskininkai 1907, the same place and year as this painting. Looking at this painting and this score side by side, we assume that Čiurlionis was trying to express music in painting and painting in music. It is unclear which was created first, but we presume that they are interrelated. This is also not very clear; however, the quaver (eighth note) on the left side of the second staff (staff) of the music score on the right looks very similar to the oddly shaped object on the left side of the second line of the painting "Allegro". This is just my subjective opinion; however, I think that Čiurlionis drew it as a landmark to let us know that he had expressed music in the painting. In addition to this, we could see some traces that he might have been trying to express the rhythm of the music by the width of the trees and the number of their branches. Since Prelude VL 307 is in F minor (f-moll), its sound is unstable and unclear, and we speculate that Čiurlionis was attempting to express painting *Allegro* with the Prelude VL 307 as well.

6. Influence of *Japonisme* and musical elements in “Andante” from *Sonata of the Spring*

Finally, let us take a look at the painting of Čiurlionis’ “Andante” from *Sonata of the Spring* (1907, Fig. 11-1). Since such a windmill did not exist in Japan at that time, it seems to be the most distant from *Japonisme* paintings with musical titles; however, as we have seen with the “Allegro”, our consideration of the “Andante” also reveals both *Japonisme* influences and musical elements, which we will discuss in detail here.

First of all, regarding the influence of *Japonisme* in “Andante”, although there seems to be no direct adoption of motifs from *ukiyo-e* prints in this painting, as we have seen, this painting also seems to have a deep connection with the creative composition of Japanese *ukiyo-e* prints, such as the graphically arranged motifs of blades of windmills and clouds in juxtaposition and contrast. In addition, the unique arrangement of linear motifs in this painting is also related to the musical notation. Again, let me introduce Prof. Landsbergis’s theory on Čiurlionis’ graphic design:

In Čiurlionis’s music we can detect groups of related linear motives resembling basic functional (and probably symbolic) antinomies. A graphic symbolism more important than any of the depicted objects is likewise evident in his pictures. In one type of symbolism, objects are set into some hidden ellipse or triangle, for example. In another, the artist sees the linear kinship of things in themselves, and even abstracts the line from the thing. In a third variant, the line is the imprint left by the artist’s own hand or musical imagination. Such an abstract linear symbolism, representing only movement and aspiration, is also a means of direct expression. Graphic design - a line in space - thereby becomes an artistic principle. It is present in both music and painting, linking the two together.

Thus, not by means of manifestos or aesthetic treatises, by his work itself, Čiurlionis asserts that all human art is one.¹⁴

This quote from Landsbergis’s theory also led me to a hypothesis that Čiurlionis might have represented blades of a windmill and the ridge line of windmills built on the ground in *Andante* with the score of the Piano piece

14 Landsbergis, V. 1992, p. 118.

Prelude in D minor (d-moll) VL 308. The reason for this is that Prelude in D minor VL308 (1907, Fig. 11-2), which was composed right after the piano piece Prelude VL307, might also have been painted with this painting “Andante” is because this Prelude VL 308 is composed in an unusual time signature, 6/4, which is not found in any other of Čiurlionis’s preludes, and it matches the number of blades of the windmill “4” and clouds “6” in the “Andante”. Also, it is just my hypothesis, however, the sound pattern of the quavers (eighth notes) in the first stave (staff) of Prelude VL308 looks like the graphics of the shape of blades of the windmill, and the sound pattern of the quavers (eighth notes) at the bottom of the score resembles the ridge line of windmills built on the ground in “Andante”. The Prelude VL 308, like VL 307, also has an unstable and indistinct sound, so we can assume that Čiurlionis was attempting to express a painting with music and *vice versa*.

7. Conclusion

The influence of *Japonisme* on Čiurlionis’s paintings was first mentioned by Ichiro Kato in 1976 and has been studied by me since 2011. In my research in Poland, I also investigated the question of where Čiurlionis first encountered the *ukiyo-e* prints of Hokusai and Hiroshige, which Kato did not pursue, and found two exhibitions of Japanese art that Čiurlionis might have seen: the first exhibition was of Japanese *ukiyo-e* prints held in J. Kriwult’s salon in 1900-01, and the second, the exhibition of Feliks Jasiński’s famous collection of Japanese arts, was at the beginning of 1901. Further research into the *ukiyo-e* prints in the Jasiński collection led to the discovery that some fragments of *ukiyo-e* by Hokusai and Hiroshige were adopted in the Čiurlionis paintings, the results of which were published in my research paper in 2015.

The main theme of this article, “Andante”, “Allegro”, “Scherzo”, and “Finale” from Čiurlionis’s series of paintings *Sonata of the Spring*, has given me the opportunity to explore once again the works of Japanese art in the Jasiński Feliks collection. This time, after reviewing the Jasiński collection, and examining the compositional elements of Čiurlionis paintings with a focus on these four paintings, I have newly discovered influence from Japanese *Nikuhitsu-ga*, the original

painting of Watanabe Seitei titled *Summer. Blooming wisteria and fish* in Čiurlionis's paintings "Scherzo" from *Sonata of the Spring*, as well as *Winter VIII* from the cycle of eight paintings *Winter*, in addition to the influence from *ukiyo-e* prints.

Of course, Čiurlionis himself never claimed to have seen this artwork, therefore the influence of *Japonisme* on his paintings is only hypotheses of mine, but given that Seitei's original painting is included in the same Jasieński collection as other *ukiyo-e* prints of Hokusai and Hiroshige which we have seen in this article strongly suggests this possibility.

The influence of and similarities to Whistler in the paintings of Čiurlionis were already discussed in my article published in 2015; however, this research has allowed us to explore further similarities and deeper considerations. Čiurlionis and Whistler had three things in common: they both gave musical titles to their paintings, they were both influenced by Hiroshige's *ukiyo-e*, and they both used a pale blue green colour in their paintings that had not previously been used in Western painting. It is not certain whether Čiurlionis was influenced by Whistler, or if it was just a coincidence that these three points were found in common between the paintings of both artists; however the research carried out for this article has made it possible to reconfirm the evidence.

Furthermore, if we consider the aspects of Čiurlionis's paintings that are not found in Whistler's works, we could see that Čiurlionis incorporated many of the graphic fragments of *ukiyo-e* prints into the composition of his paintings. Moreover, although Whistler was able to express music in his paintings, he was not a composer and could not express his paintings in music. In this respect, Čiurlionis, who was also a composer, succeeded in expressing painting in music.

At first glance, the two paintings "Allegro" and "Andante" from *Sonata of the Spring* seem to be just paintings with musical titles; however, as also suggested by Prof. Landsbergis, Čiurlionis was not satisfied with that, and tried to express music with paintings and paintings with music. The two musical examples shown with the painting "Allegro" and the music score of Prelude in F minor (f-moll) VL 307, and with the painting "Andante" and the Prelude in D minor (d-moll) VL 308 in this article are only hypothetical; however, if Čiurlionis was actually trying to express music through painting and painting

through music, then that would have been his true attitude as a composer and painter.

The main result of my research this time was the discovery of musical elements in the graphic paintings of Čiurlionis's "Allegro" and "Andante" from *Sonata of the Spring*, which were also deeply connected with *Japonisme*. As a composer and painter, Čiurlionis was able to surpass Whistler in expressing painting with music and music with painting.

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JAPONIZMO ĮTAKA IR MUZIKINIAI ELEMENTAI M. K. ČIURLIONIO
PAVEIKSLŲ CIKLE „PAVASARIO SONATA“

Summary

Japonizmo įtaka Mikalojaus Konstantino Čiurlionio (1875–1911), jo amžininkų ir Europos tapytojų impresionistų tapybai trumpai tyrinėjama nuo 2011 m., dažnai minima dabartinio autoriaus straipsniuose. Šiame straipsnyje pirmiausia apžvelgiama japonizmo įtaka Čiurlionio paveikslų serijai *Pavasario sonata*, kuri, matyt, kilusi iš japonų *ukiyo-e*, medžio blokelių estampų ir *Nikuhitsu-ga*, originalių japonų paveikslų Felikso JasieŃskio kolekcijoje, kurią Čiurlionis tikriausiai matė būdamas Lenkijoje. Be to, kadangi šie paveiksliukai „Allegro“, „Andante“, „Scherzo“ ir „Finale“ turi muzikinius pavadinimus, straipsnyje svarstoma, kodėl jis nusprendė savo paveikslams suteikti muzikinius pavadinimus, ir apie tų pavadinimų ryšį su paveikslo kompozicija, taip pat juose randamus muzikinius elementus.

Raktažodžiai: Čiurlionis, Whistleris, Landsbergis, Hokusai, Hiroshige, *ukiyo-e*, Japonizmas.